

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Recent Changes in Knowledge Management Post Lpg Era

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ABSTRACT

Developments in the global market, particularly in a variety of business firms have led every marketing process into a more advanced and innovative system. Considering all of the changes and learning that has been accomplished in the business field of study during the past two decades, a few significant things are acknowledged for the creation of new knowledge. Moreover, revolution of strategic methods to achieve an organization's. Common goal has been shown during the past two decades Real profitability in every 'for-profit' organization or business firm has been acquired through globalization, which increases the connectivity of every marketing field. Knowledge management played a pivotal role in managing success in which the presence of technological systems and human methodologies was inevitable, indeed. Therefore, this shows the varieties of strategies in obtaining the real profitability in the world of business while acknowledging a few significant things that lead to the creation of new knowledge.

Keywords: Globalization, Knowledge Management, Recognize, Revolution, political repercussions, Emphasize

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1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge Management is one of the hottest topics today in both the industry world and information research world. In our daily life, we deal with huge amount of data and information. Data and information is not knowledge until we know how to dig the value out of it. This is the reason we need knowledge management. Unfortunately, there's no universal definition of knowledge management, just as there's no agreement as to what constitutes knowledge in the first place. We chose the following definition for knowledge management for its simplicity and broad context.

DEFINITION:

Knowledge Management (KM) refers to a multi-disciplined approach to achieving organizational objectives by making the best use of knowledge. KM focuses on processes such as acquiring, creating and sharing knowledge and the cultural and technical foundations that support them.

Knowledge management may be viewed in terms of:

People – how do you increase the ability of an individual in the organization to influence others with their knowledge?

Processes – Its approach varies from organization to organization. There is no limit on the number of processes

Technology – It needs to be chosen only after all the requirements of a knowledge management initiative have been established.

Culture –The biggest enabler of successful knowledge-driven organizations is the establishment of a knowledge-focused culture

Structure – the business processes and organizational structures that facilitate knowledge sharing

Technology – a crucial enabler rather than the solution.

The implications of knowledge management:

database users: From business class users to the general public, database users will enjoy a new level of interaction with the KM system including just-in-time knowledge that delivers precise relevant information on demand and in context. More complex, smart systems will translate to optimal usability and less time spent searching for relevant information. For example, data analysts will enjoy simplified access and more powerful tools for data exploitation. The use of knowledge bases can reduce customer service costs by providing customers with easy access to 24/7 self service via smart systems that reduce the need to contact customer service or technical support staff. Database users may even create customized views of knowledge bases that support their needs.

Database Developers: The design and development of knowledge based systems will be considerably more complex than current database development methods. Developers must consider the overall technical

architecture of the corporation to ensure seamless interoperability. The use of standardized metadata and methods will also facilitate both intra-corporate and inter-corporate interoperability. Making effective physical storage and platform choices will be equally more complex. Both knowledge base developers and administrators must understand the role of the knowledge base in the overall KM system.

Database Administrators: Database Administrators will evolve into Knowledge Managers. The knowledge base will store and maintain corporate memory and Knowledge Managers will become the gatekeepers of corporate knowledge. The lines between technical roles such as Web Developer, Data Analyst or Systems Administrator will blur as these systems merge into and overlap with KM systems. DBAs will need to have some knowledge about each of these disciplines.

General Public: Even if they are not interacting directly with a knowledge base, the general public will benefit from the secondary effects of improved customer service due to faster access to more accurate information by service providers.

The Effects of Lpg on Knowledge Management

Knowledge management has generated new organisational roles and responsibilities due to the effects of LPG on knowledge management. Such as the Chief Knowledge Officer. In recent years, Personal knowledge management (PKM) practice has arisen in a way which individuals apply KM practice to themselves; this will change their role in the organisation and will be beneficial for their career development and growth.

Another impact of LPG on knowledge management that it has been widely applied to all industrial sectors, and increasingly to Government, Knowledge Management is a continually evolving discipline, with a wide range of contributions and a wide range of views on what represents good practice in Knowledge Management.

After post LPG era Knowledge Management programs are closely related to Organizational Learning initiatives, Knowledge Management may be distinguished from Organizational Learning by its greater focus on the management of specific knowledge assets and development and cultivation of the channels through which knowledge flows.

Knowledge Management is slowly gaining momentum in all organisations and also contributing to the overall development of the organisation's growth rate. Every sector, be it public or private has a purpose for using the knowledge management tool.

The most important aspect of impact of LPG Knowledge Management is technology. Technology is used to help manage, share the Knowledge. Once human communities are working well within organisations and wider networks, you can start applying technology to

facilitate the capture and sharing of knowledge. Unlike information, knowledge is embedded in people and knowledge creation occurs in the process of social interactions.

CONCLUSION:

Organizations are being forced to consider the options that will help them gain a competitive advantage against their competition and grow profits as a result of e-business, globalization, deregulation, and the merger and acquisition environment. As a result of the growing Competitive environment, management is looking at knowledge management as a means to make their Organizations more productive by leveraging their employees' intellectual capital.

The ability to harness knowledge will not only help the company's bottom line but will also help the company retain expertise in a tight job market. By not adopting a knowledge management program, companies run the

risk of being stuck in an information overloaded environment and getting left behind by the competition that understands the importance of leveraging knowledge.

While knowledge management is gaining popularity, companies need help developing solutions and will require the vendors' solutions and support. As a result of this growing awareness, we are going to see rapid growth in the demand for knowledge management services. As companies begin implementation of pilot programs, employees will learn knowledge management's benefits, be trained on technology, and become comfortable with information sharing.

Reference

1. Schmidt Lucinda, 2001, 'Collective Wisdom: the word spread', *Business Review Weekly*, February 23, Vol 22, No 7, pp 82-84.
2. Vargas Llosa Mario, 2001, 'Global Good', *The Age*, February 24, Extra 2.
3. www.mcgraw-hill.com